

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 145

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 145

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 145:0 <i>A Psalm of Praise, of David.</i></p>	<p>Psa. 145:1 תְּהַלֵּלָהּ לְדָוִד אֲרוֹמְמֶנָּה אֱלוֹתַי</p>
<p>Psa. 145:1 I will ^aextol You, ^bmy God, O King,</p>	<p>הַמְלִיךָ וְאַבְרַכְתָּה שְׁמִיךָ לְעוֹלָם וָעֶד : ² בְּכָל־ יּוֹם אֲבָרְכֶךָ וְאַתְהַלֵּלָהּ שְׁמִיךָ לְעוֹלָם וָעֶד : ³</p>
<p>And I will ^cbless Your name forever and ever.</p>	<p>גָּדוֹל יְהוָה וּמְהִלָּל מְאֹד וְלֹגְדָלְתּוֹ אֵינן חֶקֶר : ⁴ דָּוָר לְדָוָר יִשְׁבַּח מִעֲשֵׂיךָ וּגְבוּרֹתֶיךָ יִגִּידוּ :</p>
<p>² Every day I will bless You,</p>	<p>⁵ תִּדְרַר כְּבוֹד הַדָּוָה וְדַבְּרֵי נִפְלְאוֹתֶיךָ</p>
<p>And I will ^apraise Your name forever and ever.</p>	<p>אֲשִׁיחָהּ : ⁶ וְעַזְוֵי נִוְרָאוֹתֶיךָ יֹאמְרוּ וּגְדוּלוֹתֶיךָ</p>
<p>³ "Great is the LORD, and highly to be praised,</p>	<p>[וְ]גְדוּלוֹתֶיךָ [אֲסַפְּרֶנָּה : ⁷ זְכַר רַב־טוֹבוֹךָ</p>
<p>And His ^bgreatness is unsearchable.</p>	<p>יִבְיְעוּ וְצָדִיקְתֶּךָ יִרְגְּנוּ : ⁸ חֲנּוּן וּרְחָמִים יְהוָה אֲרֵךְ אֲפָיִם וּגְדוֹל־חֶסֶד : ⁹ טוֹב־יְהוָה לְכָל־</p>
<p>⁴ One ^ageneration shall praise Your works to another,</p>	<p>וְרַחֲמָיו עַל־כָּל־מִעֲשָׂיו : ¹⁰ יוֹדוּךָ יְהוָה כָּל־ מִעֲשֵׂיךָ וְחִסְדֵיךָ יִבְרַכּוּכָהּ : ¹¹ כְּבוֹד</p>
<p>And shall declare Your mighty acts.</p>	<p>מִלְכוּתֶךָ יֹאמְרוּ וּגְבוּרֹתֶךָ יִדְבְּרוּ : ¹²</p>
<p>⁵ On the ^aglorious ¹splendor of Your majesty</p>	<p>לְהוֹדִיעַ וְלִבְנֵי הָאָדָם גְּבוּרֹתֶיךָ וְכְבוֹד הַדָּרַךְ מִלְכוּתוֹ : ¹³ מִלְכוּתֶךָ מִלְכוּת כָּל־עֲלָמִים</p>
<p>And ^bon Your wonderful works, I will meditate.</p>	<p>וּמְמוֹשְׁלֹתֶיךָ בְּכָל־דָּוָר וְדָוָר : ¹⁴ סוֹמְךָ יְהוָה לְכָל־הַנִּפְלְאִים וְזוֹךְךָ לְכָל־הַכְּפֹפִים : ¹⁵</p>
<p>⁶ Men shall speak of the ¹power of Your ^aawesome acts,</p>	<p>עֵינַי־כָּל אֱלֹהִים יִשְׁבְּרוּ וְאַתָּה גוֹתֶנן לָהֶם אֶת־ אֲכָלֶם בְּעֵתוֹ : ¹⁶ פּוֹתַח אֶת־יְדֶיךָ וּמִשְׁפִּיעַ</p>
<p>And I will ^btell of Your greatness.</p>	<p>לְכָל־תֵּי רְצוֹן : ¹⁷ צַדִּיק יְהוָה בְּכָל־דְּרָכָיו</p>
<p>⁷ They shall ¹eagerly utter the memory of Your ^aabundant goodness</p>	<p>וְחֶסֶד בְּכָל־מִעֲשָׂיו : ¹⁸ קַרֹּב יְהוָה לְכָל־ קִרְאוֹ לְכָל אֲשֶׁר יִקְרָאָהוּ בְּאַמֶּת : ¹⁹ רְצוֹן־</p>
<p>And will ^bshout joyfully of Your righteousness.</p>	<p>וְרָאוּ יַעֲשֶׂה וְאֶת־שׁוֹעֲתֶם יִשְׁמַע וַיּוֹשִׁיעֶם : ²⁰ שׁוֹמֵר יְהוָה אֶת־כָּל־אֲהַבָּיו וְאֶת כָּל־</p>
<p>Psa. 145:8 The LORD is ^agracious and merciful;</p>	<p>הַרְשָׁעִים יִשְׁמִיד : ²¹ תְּהַלֵּלֵת יְהוָה יִדְבַּר־פִּי וְיִבְרַךְךָ כָּל־בְּשָׂר שֶׁם קִרְשׁוֹ לְעוֹלָם וָעֶד :</p>
<p>Slow to anger and great in lovingkindness.</p>	
<p>⁹ The LORD is ^agood to all,</p>	

And His ^bmercies are over all His works.

¹⁰ ^aAll Your works shall give thanks to You, O LORD,

And Your ^bgodly ones shall bless You.

¹¹ They shall speak of the ^aglory of Your kingdom

And talk of Your power;

¹² To ^amake known to the sons of men ¹Your mighty acts

And the ^bglory of the majesty of ¹Your kingdom.

¹³ Your kingdom is ¹an ^aeverlasting kingdom,

And Your dominion *endures* throughout all generations.

Psa. 145:14 The LORD ^asustains all who fall

And ^braises up all who are bowed down.

¹⁵ The eyes of all ¹look to You, And You ^agive them their food in due time.

¹⁶ You ^aopen Your hand And satisfy the desire of every living thing.

Psa. 145:17 The LORD is ^arighteous in all His ways

And kind in all His deeds.

¹⁸ The LORD is ^anear to all who call upon Him,

To all who call upon Him ^bin truth.

¹⁹ He will ^afulfill the desire of those who fear Him;

He will also ^bhear their cry and will save them.

²⁰ The LORD ^akeeps all who love Him,

<p>But all the ^bwicked He will destroy. ²¹ My ^amouth will speak the praise of the LORD, And ^ball flesh will ^cbless His holy name forever and ever.</p>	
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References

Psalm 145:1

^aPs 30:1; 66:17

^bPs 5:2

^cPs 34:1

Psalm 145:2

^aPs 71:6

Psalm 145:3

^aPs 48:1; 86:10; 147:5

^bJob 5:9; 9:10; 11:7; Is 40:28; Rom 11:33

Psalm 145:4

^aPs 22:30, 31; Is 38:19

Psalm 145:5

¹Or *majesty of Your splendor*

^aPs 145:12

^bPs 119:27

Psalm 145:6

¹Or *strength*

^aDeut 10:21; Ps 66:3; 106:22

^bDeut 32:3

Psalm 145:7

¹Or *bubble over with*

^aPs 31:19; Is 63:7

^bPs 51:14

Psalm 145:8

^aEx 34:6; Num 14:18; Ps 86:5, 15; 103:8

Psalm 145:9

^aPs 100:5; 136:1; Jer 33:11; Nah 1:7; Matt 19:17; Mark 10:18

^bPs 145:15

Psalm 145:10

^aPs 19:1; 103:22

^bPs 68:26

Psalm 145:11

^aJer 14:21

Psalm 145:12

¹Lit *His*

^aPs 105:1

^bPs 145:5; Is 2:10, 19, 21

Psalm 145:13

¹Lit *a kingdom of all ages*

^aPs 10:16; 29:10; 1 Tim 1:17; 2 Pet 1:11

Psalm 145:14

^aPs 37:24

^bPs 146:8

Psalm 145:15

¹Lit *wait*; or *hope for*

^aPs 104:27; 136:25

Psalm 145:16

^aPs 104:28

Psalm 145:17

^aPs 116:5

Psalm 145:18

^aDeut 4:7; Ps 34:18; 119:151

^bJohn 4:24

Psalm 145:19

^aPs 21:2; 37:4

^bPs 10:17; Prov 15:29; 1 John 5:14

Psalm 145:20

^aPs 31:23; 91:14; 97:10

^bPs 9:5; 37:38

Psalm 145:21

^aPs 71:8

^bPs 65:2; 150:6

^cPs 145:1, 2

Targum

Psa. 145:1 A psalm of David. I will exalt you, O my God the king, and I will bless your name for ages upon ages. ² Every day I will bless you and I will praise your name for ages upon ages. ³ Great is the LORD and very praiseworthy; and there is no end to his greatness. ⁴ Each generation will praise your work to the next, and they will tell of your wonders. ⁵ The splendor of the glory of your majesty, and the words of your wonders, I will speak. ⁶ And they will utter the strength of your fear, and they will tell of your greatness. ⁷ They will spread abroad the memory of your abundant goodness, and they will praise your generosity. ⁸ Compassionate and merciful is the LORD, putting away anger and doing many good things. ⁹ The LORD is good to all, and his mercies are over all his works. ¹⁰ All your works shall give you thanks, O LORD, and your pious ones shall bless you. ¹¹ They will utter the glory of your kingdom, and will speak of your might. ¹² To make known his powerful deeds to the sons of men, and the glorious splendor of his kingdom. ¹³ Your kingdom is a kingdom of all ages, and your dominion is in every generation. ¹⁴ The LORD supports all who have fallen, and lifts up all who are bowed down. ¹⁵ The eyes of all look hopefully to you, and you give them their food in its season. ¹⁶ You open your hand, and satisfy the desire of every living thing. ¹⁷ The LORD is just in all his ways, and gracious in all his works. ¹⁸ The LORD is near to all who call on him, to all who call on him in truth. ¹⁹ He will do the will of those who fear him, and he will hear their petition and redeem them. ²⁰ The LORD protects all who love him, but he will destroy all the wicked. ²¹ My mouth will speak the praise of the LORD, and all the sons of flesh will bless his holy name for ages upon ages.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm is arranged with the first word of each verse are the initial letter of the alphabet in alphabetical order. This work is fundamental, as basic as the alphabet. The Psalm also emphasizes the LORD's most crucial function is to supply the physical needs of all creation.

Notes on this Psalm

Humans are stewards of the LORD's creation. Since material items from Earth cannot be taken, in to the Lower Waters of Heaven the person owning the item is a steward. The gold that David had as King is somewhere today. The same thing applies to everything material. That is why it is important to develop spirituality. This is the one thing that your soul can take from Earth into the Lower Waters. It is an essential part of the reason humanity is here on earth. Too many people ignore their spirituality. This mainly comprises knowing about the LORD, learning the ways of the LORD, and offering praise to the LORD.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

